

Visual White Space and Emotional Exclusivity: A Student Exercise

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Abstract

In graphic design, white space (often known as negative space) is an important design parameter which when uncontrolled, can appear to be a non-designed void. However, when implemented with sensitivity, it is a visual effect that can elicit powerful emotional associations in the viewer. This study attempts to gain insight into how white space triggers certain emotional associations: good design, exclusivity, uniqueness, high quality and simplicity. To test these associations of white space, I held a class exercise for master-level Industrial Design Engineering students at NTNU. The exercise involved placing self-created CD covers on a research tool used primarily for marketing research: the dual-axis value matrix. Per my hypothesis, some students felt that prominent amounts of white space serve as a visual stimulus for objects, which are strongly associated with high quality. However, this exercise resulted in a heated debate among the students. I review the exercise and the resulting debate in detail in this paper. In today's world of often overwhelming visual stimuli, it appears that quiet visual compositions stand out from the crowd. Therefore it is intriguing to understand the multiple interpretations and effects of this vital (but often left to afterthought) aspect of design.

1. Introduction

The space in, around and between objects in a two-dimensional composition is known as *white space* (negative space). Graphic design teaches us that fewer elements on a page significantly increases how those elements relate to each other. This is apparent in the graphic design of Armin Hofmann [8], who often uses a minimum number of elements in his two-dimensional design. In using a minimum number of elements, each element gains greater power due to there being less distraction from extraneous visual information. When there are fewer objects on a page, there is a proportional increase in the amount of white space. This means that white space becomes a powerful compositional tool, one that the designer must control with conscious sensitivity. Yet this powerful compositional aspect is often left to an afterthought — a signal that the designer has only considered the positive elements in a composition. Please consider the remarkable balance and control of white space in the examples below:

Fig. 1: Examples of Armin Hofmann's poster art

These examples show extraordinary elegance where white space is a major factor in the interplay of positive elements. Note that the term white space does not refer to the color white only. In the examples above, white space is actually colored white in only the middle example. In the first example, the dominant white space area is colored black, whereas in the third example, there are equal amounts of white space colored both red and black.

Graceful examples of white space are rare these days. In desktop design manuals, discussion about white space is often emitted entirely or relegated to a few paragraphs. To further

degrade the power of white space, some authors have defined it as "...the empty but often active areas that are void of visual elements" [24]. Jakob Nielsen refers to this essential aspect of visual design as "unused" [19]. In spite of this apparent negativity, cultural experience tells us that humans often associate white space with good design, uniqueness, high quality, and/or exclusivity. Consider the Ipod[®], and the Apple[®] corporate profile in general: both represent an extraordinary restraint of design. They are visually uncluttered and have become associated with being *cool*. This might be due either to the popularity of the products themselves, or to the clean design, or a combination of the two.

Now imagine entering a used-clothing thrift store versus an exclusive handbag boutique. What do you see in your mind's eye? It is very likely that the thrift store will contain a large number of items tightly packed into a small space, and will look very visually dense. This is probably different from the environment you might have imagined in the exclusive boutique. Indeed, the fun of a used-clothing store is the hands-on experience: the act of digging around all the clutter, and allowing yourself to find something from all the stuff. However, I am concerned here with the *immediate impression* whereby each visual display appears to set up different emotions, associations, expectations and method of interaction.

Think of a busy webpage you may have seen recently. Some user-interfaces contain an extremely dense amount of information and visual elements. Google[®], however, demonstrates that the decisive use of prominent amounts of white space can create a powerful impression. It is extremely popular because its spacious, clean interface provides a breath of fresh air. The visual simplicity of its design differs dramatically from the constant bombardment of visual information provided by other search engines. I deduce from these examples that airiness, either in a real-space environment or in two-dimensional (2D) composition, is a powerful compositional device when applied conscientiously. It seems apparent that this airiness is also associated with emotional descriptors such as good design, exclusivity, uniqueness, high quality and simplicity.

During each fall, I teach a class entitled Visual Communication and Packaging Design for master-level Industrial Design students at NTNU. The class material covers everything from graphic design, to conventional ID projects, to short-term corporate case studies in multiple sectors. Over the semester-long course, I dedicate a substantial amount of time teaching students how to think about the white space in their compositions. Because the proper use of

white space signifies that the designer was in total control of the composition, it is imperative that we understand the emotional associations it creates. The exercise with the students represents only the first small step into my investigation of this important design parameter.

1.1 Research Questions

I would like to investigate the phenomenon of white space and exclusivity and ultimately apply the knowledge to user-interface design. I have split my primary questions into three groups, one for general white space issues and the second for white space's applicability to user-interface design. This paper (and the student exercise) deals with the emotional interpretations of white space only.

The *specific* research questions addressed in this student exercise are:

- Do people consistently associate certain visual design characteristics with certain emotions (especially white space in particular)?
- Do people agree on what constitutes simple vs. complicated design?

We can stretch these two primary questions into *general* questions about white space as a visual design tool/parameter. *General* questions about white space include:

- What is “clean, simple” design anyway? What do these terms mean visually?
- How/why does the use of prominent amounts of white space give an overall impression of exclusivity?
- At what point does filling the white space change its qualities of exclusivity?
- How can these issues be tested effectively and non-subjectively?
- What is the judgment criteria for white space? When does space become *empty*?

From there we can ask how white space is influential in the layout of a computer interface. Research questions about white space as an *electronic user-interface* design issue include:

- Do users prefer minimalistic, clean, simple user-interfaces to current compositions?
- Do users prefer the status quo, more, or less visual noise?
- How important is it to control white space when designing electronic applications? My opinion is that it is VERY important. But how does one measure and/or test for this?
- How much of a user's preference is due to conditioning (by use of current software apps)?
- Most importantly, how can software developers learn to use and control white space — a major aspect of the overall design? Is it possible to determine an optimal proportion that everyone can use (based on books where approximately 50% is white)?

In user interface applications, one must determine the balance between the visual elegance of the design and the application's functionality. After all, an application must be effective to

use. Can the use of elegant design increase the user friendliness of an application, even if it results in an increased number of clicks? Why don't major software developers utilize white space more conscientiously? Would it be practical if they did?

2. Student exercise: Dual –axis matrix

The exercise was carried out on 15 March, 2006. The dual-axis scale is a method most often used in marketing research and early product design processes. More specific than a single-axis scale, it can be used to plot out two characteristics simultaneously. Both axes are continuous and include the edges; there are **not** four distinct quadrants. Using this method in product/brand evaluation serves as a sufficient measure of subjective interpretation of a visual stimulus. For my purposes, it was necessary to use a large-scale physical prototype, as I'd asked the students to judge their newly created CD covers on the matrix. However, they were not allowed to move *their own* CD covers, only one done by someone else.

2.1 The Target CD Cover

Fig. 3: Ragnhild Nesbakken's CD cover from 2004, outside and inside

Since there are only 15 people in the class, I supplemented the selection with two CD covers that had been done by two women who had taken the class previously. Ragnhild Nesbakken took the class in 2004 and kindly allowed me to use her CD cover as a primary test object. Her solution shows an example of exquisitely controlled white space (in this case colored white). For the outside, she chose white space as the dominant visual device and coupled it with a textural component: corrugated cardboard. This creates a very subtle, delicate shadow effect — appropriate for the wintry associations she wanted to inspire. For the inside, she devised an ingenious representation for snow: styrofoam beads encased in transparent plastic

channel tubing. I decided to include Ragnhild's CD cover because I felt the conscientious design of white space held great potential for emotional associations of exclusivity. I wanted to see how it would be placed on the matrix scale.

2.2 Technique

Dual-axis matrices are often seen in small, A4 format. However, since this exercise involved a number of people who were asked to move numerous physical objects, I made a large-scale version with a white bed sheet as the background. Wooden sticks served for the axis lines and axis words were printed on A3 paper. This allowed me to change the words very easily. The students turned around while I switched the words between variations, until I gave the ok to turn back to the exercise. I announced the parameter I wanted them to think about, and then ran to the floor above to take pictures while they did the exercise. We completed five variations of this technique. The use of different terms allowed me to test for White space/Exclusivity without the students knowing it, and also allowed for slightly different semantic interpretations of each word. All but one student were native Norwegian speakers, and both the Norwegian and English words were visible on each A3 sheet.

2.3 Matrix Layout

The following matrix layouts represent the primary test issues.

First impression of design:

Visual design makes the CD look:

Overall impression of CD cover:

For the sake of comparison, I would like to present a few other CDs that I did not feel incorporated the visual use of white space as strongly as Ragnhild's.

As we can see, there are a number of different design strategies that generate all types of emotional associations. Although we could debate the use of white space in almost every one (with the exception of the globe in the lower left), I have chosen to investigate white space when represented by a prominent amount of the color WHITE. The CD in the upper left corner comes closest to incorporating white space as I've outlined it here, but since this example was so dependent on being seen from above, I decided to concentrate solely on Ragnhild's design. Still, I compare this one to hers briefly in the Results section.

3. Results

The results of these exercises are shown in the photographs below, with the parameter repeated. Ragnhild's CD cover is highlighted by a red oval.

3.1 First impression of design:

(Ragnhild's CD = red oval)

This variant was completed early in the exercise and was intended to serve as a warm-up. Because we'd held a critique the morning before the exercise, all students were aware of the materials and design choices involved in each CD cover.

The placement of Ragnhild's CD cover in this example is quite decisive. It has been placed clearly at the Neutral end of the vertical axis, and slightly towards the Playful side of the horizontal axis. The word *Neutral* was chosen as an opposite to colorful; it was my hope that *Neutral* would not have negative connotations. As we can see, the students placed covers with more visual elements towards the Playful end, and placed the covers with fewer elements towards the Serious end. This corresponds to the vertical axis as well: fewer visual elements are considered Neutral, whereas multiple elements are considered Colorful. The CD cover deemed to be most Colorful was actually opened to reveal the inside of the cover, whereas all others remained closed. This became a primary factor in the decision-making.

In some ways it was surprising that Ragnhild's CD cover was placed closer to Playful than Serious. Note the other CD cover (blue oval), made by a student in the current class. Although this CD cover displayed a comparable amount of white space, it was placed decisively towards Serious. This CD cover was made of heavy transparent plastic with gold trim; it is my suspicion that materials, size and solidity played a substantial role in its placement with reference to Ragnhild's.

3.2 Visual design makes the CD look:

(Ragnhild's CD = red oval)

For the next variant, Ragnhild's CD cover was the only one to be presented in open form. This became a matter of discussion: the students could not agree whether to judge it while open or closed. When closed, one student exclaimed it was "super-Simple!" but when open, it was placed at the extreme combination of Exclusive and Complex. The students settled quickly on the location shown above. I suspected that the styrofoam channels might have led to the students' appreciation of its complexity rather than a strict interpretation of visual design. When I raised this issue, a few students said that they'd considered both aspects.

For comparison purposes, notice where the second CD cover (blue oval) was placed, at the extreme for Exclusivity and Simple. This cover and Ragnhild's were clearly deemed Exclusive, although they are not the only ones. The other two show completely different design strategies: one is composed of light pieces of bentwood woven into an orbital shape, and the second is composed of concrete spray painted with black. The materials and visual compositions of these four compositions were so different that it is nearly impossible to deduce any commonalities between them.

It became obvious that Ragnhild's CD cover had become a focus point, and the discussion began to revolve around her CD only. The students may have felt they could speak more openly about her CD because they knew that none of their fellow classmates had created it. However, recall that there were **two** CD covers that were unknown to the students, and the other one was more or less ignored. I had chosen both CD covers because they both represented white space, but the primary color on the other CD was black, not white.

3.3 Overall impression of CD cover:

At the point of this final variant, the students had become secure in their opinions of where Ragnhild's CD belonged. Upon beginning the new variant, her cover was one of the first to be moved. However, this does not mean it stayed in one spot — the dotted red lines represent two of the many locations where her CD was placed. The discussion became fascinatingly heated, and her CD was the focus of it. The debate almost seemed to pick up where it had left off from the previous variant. Please note that her CD cover was closed for this final part of the exercise.

Although the matrix words no longer included Exclusive and Simple, it became apparent that the discussion begun in the previous variant had not been concluded.

I had not told the students that her CD was one that I was watching specifically, but it became a natural focus point for the discussion. The students began to develop strong opinions about

what makes a CD exclusive or not. I was able to note down a small part of the group conversation regarding the placement of her CD. The quotes below are taken directly from the student discussion (my translation from Norwegian):

Student 1: That one is definitely exclusive, high quality

Student 3: I got an Ipod feeling from it

Student 1: Cardboard is a cheap material, but the white color gives it a feeling of exclusivity, it could have been perfume or wine

Student 2: I think it looks cheap, see; it's made of cardboard!

Student 1: The format is boring, but the white makes it exclusive

Student 4: I agree with Student 1, it does not look cheap or common

Student 2: It's so anonymous that it becomes common. There is no convention that says that things that are white are exclusive! In addition, it looks recycled, therefore, it can NEVER be expensive. I agree that the format is boring.

Student 3: What about Apple? Doesn't that mean simplicity?

Student 2: Does white automatically mean exclusive? What if this CD were red?

Student 1: The color white means purity, it gives me a feeling of silkiness...if it were red it wouldn't be exclusive!

It is important to note that I had not told the students my intentions for doing the exercise — I had not specifically discussed the emotional implications of visual white space with them at any point. I became fascinated by the appropriateness of this discussion for my research interests. Other than using the words on the axes, I had given the students **no idea** about how to proceed with the exercise or the discussion. All conversation was impromptu and occurred very naturally. The discussion lasted for about 10 minutes and became surprisingly intense.

The photo below shows where Ragnhild's CD cover eventually ended up, although a number of students voiced their complete disagreement with the placement.

4. Discussion

At this point, I decided to interrupt the discussion and ask the students what they thought the exercise had entailed. I explained that I'd been intrigued by the heated debate that had just occurred and that I was primarily interested in the relationship between what people see as white space and how they experience it emotionally. When I stated that I'd wondered about the associations of exclusivity, the discussion continued immediately, with the only exception that I was now involved. When I asked what it is that makes a CD cover (or any visual composition) appear exclusive, the focus turned immediately back to Ragnhild's cover. The discussion then revolved around materials and how her solution had been rendered physically:

Student 2: It looks like trash, something that someone throws away. Cardboard is a material intended to stiffen boxes, it's only a part of the packaging.

Student 4: Talk about something that creates different impressions: material vs. visual design!

Student 5: If something is plain white, the details become very important. What wrecks this for me is the imprecise edge on the outside.

Student 3: Can we please look beyond the materials?

Student 1: Very, very nice. This is one of the finest CD covers here. The color is pure, clean and exclusive. Black is exclusive too, but not pink.

Student 3: It's the overall impression that counts!

This dialogue clearly shows that some students interpreted Ragnhild's CD cover based purely on an overall visual impression, while others integrated the visuals with the choice of materials. At one point someone said that materials play a huge role: magnets give a very different impression than silk cord. Indeed, at various points during the exercise, it appeared that students made placement choices with as much regard to material use as to visual design.

Although Students 1 and 3 expressed views that were closest to my hypothesis, the students reflected a variety of opinions in which all were absolutely correct. From the discussion that transpired, it is obvious that there is no wrong answer in how people interpret visual media. Indeed, the students raised the very good point that materials *do* make a difference in how people interpret a visual composition, even if some of them did not agree.

5. Conclusion and future work

The students demonstrated that white space is an important design consideration. The emotional relationship between white space and exclusivity became a charged and controversial discussion among 12 design students. Without knowing my research questions, these students clearly demonstrated that the primary research questions were on target:

- Do people consistently associate certain visual design characteristics with certain emotions (especially white space in particular)?

From this experience, it appears that people do not associate white space with certain emotions consistently. But because this was an experiment conducted by *a group* of students (where anyone could place the CD according to his/her opinion), it is impossible to determine individual emotional associations. Such findings could be accomplished by a different test format, whereby a student performed the same test, but only as a single participant. A single-

participant test method would better reflect individual associations of white space with certain emotions. That will very likely become a follow-up test.

- Do people agree on what constitutes simple vs. complicated design?

Definitely not for this study! It was clear that once the debate began, the students divided themselves into two groups: those who felt that white space reflects simplicity, and those who didn't. It became apparent to me that I was witnessing the students forming their individual opinions on this topic. As above, I intend to use a single-participant test method to see if people do agree more than they seemed to in this exercise. I wondered if some of the students were playing devil's advocate and simply creating a debate. I don't think so, but a single-participant test with averaged results would likely determine this better.

The students' debate raised a number of very specific questions, something that I'd hoped would arise from this exercise. Student 2 phrased my primary concern perfectly by asking "Is there a convention that says that white space automatically means exclusive?" There is clearly room for more research in this area. We may assume that a relationship between a design parameter (white space) and an emotional association (exclusivity) may be consistent and predictable, but the students showed that this is not the case.

Regardless of the emotions it triggers, white space is an active part of a composition, even though it is the space around, in between objects. When applied successfully, it is not simply negative space, which implies that it is an empty void and lacks purpose. Rather, it becomes a necessary, complementary aspect to positive elements. When used sensitively and conscientiously, white space is a powerful design parameter. When applied less successfully, it can appear empty, as though it lacks purpose and was designed as an afterthought.

Future work involves testing this phenomenon in more targeted, controlled manner. I am not sure that the dual-axis matrix is the ideal method to use, but it allows for subjective rather than specific interpretation. Another issue to be determined is the fine line between *intentionally designed* white space and that which is non-designed (an afterthought). Is there a way to test for people's interpretation of this? Can people tell the difference? Is there a way to help designers make the difference clear? Other questions also deal with very fine distinctions:

- How much white space does it take to push the object into the realm of being *exclusive*?
Is there a fixed proportion?
- Why is this phenomenon apparently true? What does cognitive psychology have to contribute to understanding why?

Although there is clearly room for more research into the relationship between white space and exclusivity, this does not detract from the power of white space as an important tool in visual design. I firmly believe that white space must be given a proactive role in all types of compositional design, especially in electronic applications, where information must be relayed quickly and effectively. To do this, it is necessary to understand the relationship between white space and the various emotional associations it creates: particularly those that suggest exclusivity.

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